

1 **Perceptions of cultural ecosystem services of tree-based green infrastructure: A focus**
2 **group participatory mapping in Zagreb, Croatia**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 Urban green infrastructure provides city dwellers numerous benefits. Among them, cultural
14 ecosystem services (CES) are distinguished by being easily perceived and essential for people
15 and their well-being. However, not all CES are equally easy to perceive, resulting with some
16 of the CES categories being weakly explored. Research on CES also rarely considers
17 elements of urban green infrastructure other than parks and forests. Therefore, there is a lack
18 of research on different components of urban green infrastructure, especially tree-based,
19 perceived in relation to CES. This paper presents the results of focus group participatory
20 mapping implemented with citizens in the city districts of Zagreb on the perception of five
21 selected CES categories in various types of urban green infrastructure. Our results show that
22 participants perceived 13 different types of tree-based urban green infrastructure as providers
23 of CES. We also distinguish patterns in the perception of CES categories and their connection
24 with types of tree-based urban green infrastructure. Tree lines are perceived as providers of
25 aesthetical experiences. Furthermore, forests and park forests are perceived in relation to
26 place attachment and recreational activities, while parks are versatile and provide all explored
27 CES. Other types that emerged as important were greenways, greenery around residential
28 buildings and educational institutions, which provokes rethinking of a careful planning of the
29 entire repertoire of urban green infrastructure.

30 Keywords: aesthetics; correspondence analysis; cultural identity; educational services; place
31 attachment; recreation

32

33 **1. Introduction**

34 Urban green spaces are an important element in cities and contribute to improving the health
35 and well-being of city residents. Urban green infrastructure (UGI) is planned and managed to
36 provide various ecosystem services. It also helps in mitigating environmental issues and
37 improve the quality of life in cities (Haase et al., 2014). When addressing ecosystem services
38 provided by UGI, monetary and non-monetary valuation methods of UGI benefits may be
39 applied, but they do not directly account for human needs or preferences (ibid.). However,
40 stakeholder involvement is a valuable addition to standard data gathering methods by bearing
41 local knowledge and enhancing the assessment results (Fagerholm et al., 2012). It is
42 especially important when assessing cultural ecosystem services (CES), defined as
43 ‘nonmaterial benefits people obtain from ecosystems’ (MEA, 2005), whose manifestation is
44 significantly influenced by people’s perception. CES are of great importance for people
45 living in cities, since they are one of the prominent contributors to the well-being (Plieninger
46 et al., 2013). However, they are difficult to assess and value (Small et al., 2017).

47 There is growing scientific interest in CES (Cheng et al., 2019). CES have been shown to be
48 essential for citizens and are constantly highly ranked in perceived importance in comparison
49 to other ecosystem services (Beichler, 2015). Still, they are not equally perceived among
50 people, e.g., aesthetics and recreation are more often and more easily perceived categories,
51 while education is a less perceived category of CES in urban areas (Beichler, 2015). Also,
52 people usually put greater general importance on recreational services in cities (Dou et al.,
53 2017; Rall et al., 2017), while studies addressing multiple CES at the same time are still
54 lacking (Cheng et al., 2019).

55 UGI is the main provider of CES in urban areas. In that regard, parks and urban forests are
56 better explored in relation to CES provision (Bertram and Rehdanz, 2015; Hegetschweiler et
57 al., 2017; Korpilo et al., 2018; Zwierzchowska et al., 2018; Baumeister et al., 2020). In
58 general, parks are usually perceived as providers of passive or low intensity recreation, social
59 opportunities and cultural heritage values across different cities in Europe (Bertram and
60 Rehdanz, 2015; Rall et al., 2017; Zwierzchowska et al., 2018; Vierikko et al., 2020). Urban
61 forests are perceived as providers of recreational opportunities, aesthetic and cultural heritage

62 values, with strong reminiscent character (Arnberger, 2006; Baumeister et al., 2020; Kičić et
63 al., 2020). Biodiversity, education and experiences in nature, as well as aesthetics and
64 spirituality are found as the emerging characteristics perceived in forests (Plieninger et al.,
65 2013; Rall et al., 2017). Restoration, heritage values, sentient and their quiet character are
66 connected with the perception of cemeteries as unique green spaces in cities (Nordh et al.,
67 2017; Pietrzyk-Kaszyńska et al., 2017). There is a gap in literature reflected in the scarcity of
68 papers dealing with the connection between CES and other types of UGI, especially those
69 which are tree-based such as tree lines, greenery around educational facilities or
70 neighbourhood greenery (but see Rall et al., 2017; Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). Knowledge
71 about the perception and use of other UGI types exists; however, it does not always employ
72 the CES framework, e.g., in the case of urban stream corridors (Scott Shafer et al., 2013;
73 Garcia et al., 2017), neighbourhood greenery (Säumel et al., 2021), and the perception of
74 trees in urban areas (Graça et al., 2018; Fernandes et al., 2019). Therefore, it would be
75 beneficial for scientific literature and local management to identify comprehensively how the
76 perception and use of CES are related to various types of tree-based UGI. Comprehensive
77 overview of perception and use of different types of tree-based UGI allows for tree and green
78 space management practices to be refined and enhanced contributing to increased quality of
79 green areas and subsequently citizens' wellbeing.

80 Since CES are essentially intangible, revealing provision locations is a vital part of their
81 mainstreaming into spatial planning practices (Ives et al., 2017). It is important to consider
82 the perception and use of those at the receiving end of ecosystem benefits, i.e. users (Brown
83 and Fagerholm, 2015). One of the useful approaches to collect information on perception and
84 its spatial distribution is participatory mapping. It can help facilitate the manifestation of
85 intangible ecosystem services such as CES in a visible form (Hernández-Morcillo et al.,
86 2013). It can be implemented by using different methods such as focus groups (Lowery and
87 Morse, 2013), group mapping (Beichler, 2015), face-to-face interviews (Plieninger et al.,
88 2013) and small group interviews (Xu et al., 2020) to collect spatial data to identify a range
89 of values and land use issues (Brown et al., 2014a).

90 Therefore, the goals of this paper are: 1) To quantify and explore the perception of five CES
91 expressed by residents of city districts in the city of Zagreb utilizing focus group participatory
92 mapping, 2) To explore the relationship between the perception of five CES and tree-based
93 UGI throughout Zagreb's city districts.

94 The study area for this research is the City of Zagreb in Croatia, which can be considered as
95 the postsocialist city. Indeed, Zagreb is facing similar problems to those of postsocialist cities
96 in Central and Eastern Europe (Kronenberg et al., 2020). Therefore, this paper contributes to
97 a better understanding of the perception of CES in a postsocialist cultural context. Recent
98 literature review on urban forest and urban green space research in Croatia and Slovenia
99 demonstrated the existence of public perception studies, although sparse (Krajter Ostoić et
100 al., 2020b). While most of those in Croatia were conducted in Zagreb, there is a shortage of
101 studies dealing simultaneously with the perception of multiple sites and different types of
102 green spaces. However, recently, the relation between the perception of CES and tree-based
103 green spaces in Zagreb was presented based on a qualitative analysis of focus group
104 transcripts (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a).

105 We have used quantitative analysis of spatial markers collected with participatory mapping
106 during focus groups to explore and quantify the connections between tree-based UGI and
107 perceived CES in city districts in Zagreb. In doing so, we build on previous research on green
108 spaces in Zagreb together with other research on CES and UGI across Europe and expect to
109 achieve comparable novel results on the emerging perception patterns of CES and their
110 manifestation in different tree-based UGI in Zagreb.

111

112 **2. Material and methods**

113 *2.1. Study area*

114 The city of Zagreb, a Croatian capital, is located in the northwest part of the country. Zagreb
115 is the largest city in Croatia as well as the economic and political centre. It extends over of
116 641.32 km² with total population of 804,507 citizens (estimated for 2018) and an average
117 population density of 1,254 inhabitants per km² (Statistical Yearbook of the City of Zagreb
118 (SYCZ), 2019). The city is divided into 17 city districts and 218 community boards that
119 represent a form of local self-government (Fig. 1). City districts vary in size and population
120 density. Moreover, they differ based on terrain configuration, the proportion of built-up areas,
121 UGI types, and spatial distribution.

122 Forests are the most prominent type of UGI in Zagreb, is covering approx. 20,000 ha
123 (differentiated by ownership into state-owned and privately-owned in almost equal shares). In
124 addition to forests, there are other types of UGI in Zagreb (e.g., 59.2 ha of parks, 243 km of
125 tree-lined roads, and 9,492.28 ha of protected areas in various categories) (SYCZ, 2019). The

126 aforementioned UGI is under the city's funding and management, except for forests and park
127 forests which are managed by a public forest management company (Croatian Forests Ltd.).
128 Management of park forests is co-financed by the city's annual budget and the city
129 department determines management and controlling of the conducted work and its quality.
130 (Krajter Ostoić, 2013).

131 Due to the diversity of UGI types in Zagreb, here were describe only some of the bigger
132 natural areas important for the study area context. Out of 9,492.28 ha of protected areas,
133 around 8,500 ha belongs to Nature Park Medvednica located at the Medvednica mountain in
134 the north from the city and partly located within the city's borders. Park forests are forest
135 areas managed primarily for aesthetic and recreational purposes (Matić, 2010). Through
136 Zagreb also runs the Sava River, (28.7 km in length), along whose banks there is a greenway
137 that is a highly visited and presents a valuable recreational area.

138

139 Figure 1. The study area. A) Digital orthophoto of the city of Zagreb (Croatian State Geodetic
 140 Administration) with city district boundaries (Open Street Map data) and photographs
 141 representing: 1) Nature Park Medvednica (M.K.); 2) Park Forest Dotrščina (M.K.); 3) Forest
 142 (M.K.); 4) Walking path along the stream (M.K.); 5) King Tomislav Square (part of Green

143 System) (M.K.); 6) Park Maksimir (M.K.); 7) Greenway along the Sava River (S.K.O.) B)
144 Location of the study area in Croatia.

145

146 *2.2. Selected cultural ecosystem services*

147 We explored five CES categories, namely - place attachment, aesthetic experiences,
148 recreation, cultural identity, and nature education. The employed categories are based on
149 MEA (2005) classification, which is widely accepted, appropriately perceived, and used in
150 scientific practice (Riechers et al., 2016; Cheng et al., 2019). These categories allow the
151 interpretation and comparison between studies in order to explore a whole range of CES,
152 including those categories known to be difficult to capture.

153

154 *2.3. Focus group participatory mapping*

155 Implementation of participatory mapping during focus groups interviews was similar to that
156 reported in the scientific literature (Fagerholm et al., 2012; Lowery and Morse, 2013;
157 Plieninger et al., 2013; Xu et al., 2020). We organized and conducted 20 focus groups with
158 citizens of city districts, at least one in each city district in the period between 21 March and
159 11 November 2019 (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). Focus groups took place at the premises of
160 local self-government or in public libraries.

161 Each focus group was moderated according to the common protocol (the questions are
162 presented in Table 1). Along with the discussion among focus group participants that was
163 recorded and analysed separately, for which the participants gave their consent, the
164 participants were also instructed to show green spaces where they perceived or experienced
165 the CES category in question in the particular city district on a map. For mapping, colour and
166 number-coded adhesive sticker dots were placed on the map. The participants were presented
167 with the aerial map of the city district printed on an A0 sheet of paper. Aerial maps have
168 previously been a useful tool used for workshop participatory mapping (Fagerholm et al.,
169 2012). At the beginning of each focus group, the participants were introduced to the map and
170 some of the main spatial points for orientation. They did not put markers on the map but only
171 pointed to a location, while a member of the research team familiar with the coding was
172 responsible for marking those locations. When participants were unable to show the exact
173 location or sometimes had no knowledge of the name of a certain green space, they were

174 instructed to describe it, and based on that description, the location was found and marked
175 respecting the established coding protocol afterwards.

176

177 Table 1: Questions asked in focus group interviews related to specific cultural ecosystem
178 services

CES	Question
Place attachment	What are your favourite urban green spaces in your city district and why?
Recreation	What urban green spaces in your city district do you visit the most and why?
Aesthetics	Are there any urban green spaces in your city district that you find beautiful (aesthetically pleasing)? Which are those and why?
Cultural identity	Are there any urban green spaces in your city district that you find important for the district's or Zagreb's cultural identity? Which are those and why?
Education	Are there any urban green spaces in your city district that you find important for the nature education of citizens? Which are those and why?

179

180

181 After the focus group interview, the socio-demographic data of participants were collected.
182 The complete procedure of developing a focus group protocol and designing a socio-
183 demographic questionnaire is presented in (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a).

184 Spatial markers were afterwards digitized into a GIS database. For this purpose, the QGIS
185 software (v3.4.14) was used.

186

187 *2.4. Spatial and statistical analysis*

188 *2.4.1. Spatial data analysis*

189 Spatial markers were digitized respecting the CES category and coding. This allowed the
190 connection of spatial data with participants' socio-demographic characteristics later in the
191 analysis.

192 We delineated types of UGI under or near the digital markers using GIS. As a base layer, we
193 used publicly available spatial datasets from the City of Zagreb as a reference
194 (<https://geoportal.zagreb.hr>). Researchers who are well informed about the study area and
195 moderated focus groups categorized UGI types marked by the participants. Categorization

196 was accepted among the research team as representative for the study area. A 10 m buffer
197 was added to extend the delineated area and to include spatial markers that are likely to be
198 connected with a specific UGI type (Brown et al., 2014b).

199 Since tree-based UGI was the focus of this research, a subset of delineated areas containing
200 trees resulted with tree-based UGI. For spatial analysis, we overlapped the tree-based UGI
201 with layers of digitized markers representing CES. The frequency of placed markers of CES
202 categories in each tree-based UGI type was calculated. Due to spatial diversity of city
203 districts and a varied number of participants in focus groups, spatial markers were analysed
204 based on the UGI type for the city as a whole.

205

206 2.4.2. Statistical data analysis

207 Descriptive statistics were performed on the collected spatial data and participants' socio-
208 demographic data. We associated participant's socio-demographic information with the
209 placed markers. To determine the number of participants who spatially perceived CES in a
210 tree-based UGI, we assigned binary codes (1 = perceived, 0 = not perceived) to participants
211 for each CES category separately.

212 To conduct correspondence analysis (CA) we used a contingency table of collected markers
213 of CES categories in each tree-based UGI type (see Table 3). CA is performed to explore the
214 relationship among multiple categorical data (Sourial et al., 2010; Bachi et al., 2020; Xu et
215 al., 2020). The resulting CA biplot is a visual representation of the categorical data and their
216 association, where the distance between variables represents relationships between them (Xu
217 et al., 2020). The results were further complemented by calculating Spearman's rank
218 correlation coefficients between CES and the associated tree-based UGI types using the same
219 contingency table, resulting in a measure of statistical strength among the explored variables
220 (Plieninger et al., 2013; Fagerholm et al., 2019; Bachi et al., 2020).

221 Statistical analyses were performed in R software (v3.6.2) using *FactoMineR* (Lê et al.,
222 2008), *factoextra* (Kassambra and Mundt, 2020), and *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) packages.

223

224

225

226 **3. Results**

227 *3.1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants and CES perception*

228 Altogether, 94 participants participated in focus groups. Socio-demographic profile of the
229 participants is presented in Table 2. The majority were females and were highly educated
230 (from undergraduate to PhD). More than half of the respondents were employed, while the
231 rest were unemployed or retired. Prior to the focus groups, many had been living in Zagreb or
232 in their respective city district for a long time. Two thirds of the respondents lived in
233 apartment buildings.

234 Table 2. Socio-demographic profile of focus group participants

Variable	Category	N	%
Gender	Female	54	57%
	Male	40	43%
Age (years)	<i>Mean</i>	54	
	<i>Min</i>	26	
	<i>Max</i>	83	
Education	Elementary	3	3%
	Secondary	29	31%
	Higher	62	61%
Work Status	Employed	52	55%
	Unemployed/Retired	42	45%
Living in Zagreb (year)	<i>Mean</i>	43	
Living in city district (year)	<i>Mean</i>	33	

235

236 *3.2. The proportion of perceived and mapped CES*

237 The number of the collected spatial markers included in the analysis is 588 (Table 3). The
238 highest number of markers was collected for place attachment, followed by aesthetics and
239 recreational services. The smallest number of markers was associated with cultural identity
240 and education (Table 4). Most of the participants were able to identify locations they perceive
241 as bearing place attachment, followed by aesthetics and recreation, while every other or every
242 third participant was able to identify locations perceived as those providing cultural identity
243 and educational services in a city district, respectively. For each perceived CES, more than
244 half of the participants were females.

245 Table 3. Frequency table of markers placed in a tree-based urban green space

UGI/CES	Place attachment	Aesthetics	Recreation	Cultural identity	Education	Total
Park	67	51	51	24	21	214
Forest	24	20	20	10	4	78
Park forest	32	6	15	11	4	68
Greenery of sport and recreational facilities	13	16	15	6	1	51
Treeline	16	26	4	3	1	50
Walking path along the stream	15	13	11	1	0	40
Greenway	13	9	9	2	0	33
The greenery around residential buildings	9	12	4	1	1	27
The greenery of the educational facility	4	2	2	3	3	14
Private garden	2	3	0	1	1	7
Single tree	0	3	0	0	0	3
Green system	1	0	0	0	1	2
Cemetery	0	1	0	0	0	1

246

247 Table 4. Distribution of spatial markers representing CES, the number of participants and
 248 their gender (N=94)

CES	N of markers	Proportion of markers	N of participants	% of participants	Points by gender (M / F)	Perception by gender (M / F)
Place attachment	196	33%	89	94%	41% / 59%	39% / 61%
Aesthetics	162	28%	71	75%	41% / 59%	39% / 61%
Recreation	131	22%	60	64%	47% / 53%	42% / 58%
Cultural identity	62	11%	46	49%	42% / 58%	39% / 61%
Education	37	6%	30	33%	43% / 57%	43% / 57%

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253 3.3. Relationship between perceived CES and the types of tree-based UGI

254 In total, 13 different types of tree-based UGI were identified as providers of CES (Fig. 2).
 255 The average number of markers collected for one type of tree-based UGI was 45. Types of
 256 tree-based UGI with above the average number of collected markers were parks, forests, park
 257 forests, greenery of sports and recreational facilities, tree lines, walking paths along the
 258 streams, and greenway.

259
 260 Figure 2. Frequency of spatial markers in tree-based urban green infrastructure
 261 differentiated by cultural ecosystem services (588 markers)

262
 263 Before conducting CA, a contingency table was tested to see if the data was applicable for
 264 analysis. The calculated Chi-square of independence (with Monte Carlo simulation based on
 265 1,000 replicates) between variables indicated that the data was appropriate for further
 266 analysis and interpretation ($\chi^2 = 86.96$, $p < 0.01$). CA resulted in a two-dimensional plot
 267 explaining 84.7% of the variance in the data (Fig. 3). First dimension (Dim1) explaining
 268 58.9% of variability distinguishes aesthetics was associated mostly with tree lines, greenery
 269 around residential buildings, greenway, and to a lesser extent walking paths along the streams
 270 and greenery of sports and recreational facilities from other tree-based UGI. The second
 271 dimension (Dim2) explaining an additional 25.8% of variability emphasized recreation and

272 education mainly associated with the greenway, walking paths along the streams, park
 273 forests, and greenery of sports and recreational facilities. Parks were perceived and used as
 274 versatile parts of tree-based UGI and therefore they are not linked to any CES, but rather they
 275 are providers of all CES indicated by their placement in the middle of a biplot. The cultural
 276 identity and educational services of a city district's UGI are less perceived among
 277 participants, also shown by the CA biplot. Only greenery around educational institutions,
 278 such as elementary schools and kindergartens, and a green system were perceived in
 279 connection with educational services. Complete contributions of CES and tree-based UGI to
 280 CA dimensions can be found in the Supplementary Material.

281

282 Figure 3. CA biplot of the first two axes representing a relationship between CES
 283 perception and tree-based UGI (triangles for CES, dots for tree-based UGI with abbreviations
 284 as follows: “T” – single tree, “C” – cemetery, “TL” – tree line, “GB” – greenery around
 285 residential buildings, “PG” – private garden, “WP” – walking path along the stream, “SR” –
 286 greenery of sports and recreational facilities, “GW” – greenway, “F” – forest, “P” – park,
 287 “PF” – park forest, “GEF” – greenery around educational facilities, “GS” – green system)

288

289 To explore further differences between the perception of CES categories and their
 290 distribution in a tree-based UGI, Spearman’s rank correlation was used. The results show a
 291 statistically significant ($p < .01$ for bolded values, asterix for $p < .05$) correlation among the
 292 addressed CES categories (Table 5). The highest correlation value is calculated between
 293 place attachment and recreation, meaning that people are attached to that tree-based UGI
 294 which they most frequently use for recreation and vice versa. Place attachment is also highly
 295 and significantly correlated with cultural identity, and significantly but less strongly with
 296 aesthetics and education. Aesthetics is significantly correlated with place attachment and
 297 recreation. Recreation is significantly correlated with all services but education. Cultural
 298 identity is significantly correlated with all services. Education shows a weak and non-
 299 significant correlation with other services, except with cultural identity and place attachment,
 300 which is also in line with the results of CA.

301

302 Table 5. Correlation matrix (Spearman’s rank) for mapped cultural ecosystem services

	Place attachment	Aesthetics	Recreation	Cultural identity	Education
Place attachment					
Aesthetics	0.81				
Recreation	0.92	0.81			
Cultural Identity	0.89	0.69*	0.87		
Education	0.63*	0.36	0.56	0.79	

303

304

305 4. Discussion

306 CES are rarely addressed on a city level (Hegetschweiler et al., 2017), thus this study covered
 307 the whole city of Zagreb by conducting focus groups in each city district. As a result, detailed
 308 spatial data for the entire city was gathered based on the residents’ perception of CES
 309 provided by tree-based UGI in their city districts.

310 Studies focusing on the perception of CES usually target only one or a few types of UGI,
 311 with forests and parks being the most frequent (Hegetschweiler et al., 2017). However, our
 312 participants could reflect on and map any type of UGI. As a result, participants mapped their
 313 perception of CES in relation to 13 types of tree-based UGI. Some of these were not often

314 covered in similar studies (e.g., greenery of sports and recreation facilities, cemeteries)
315 (Beichler, 2015; Ives et al., 2017; Pietrzyk-Kaszyńska et al., 2017; Riechers et al., 2019).

316 The workshop participatory mapping approach is more flexible because it combines
317 qualitative and quantitative data collection at the same time (Brown et al., 2014a). Qualitative
318 data provided clarification about locations and UGI types while digitizing collected spatial
319 markers. The approach resulted in detailed information that allowed a better understanding of
320 the perception of different tree-based UGI types and relationships with CES than it was the
321 case in previous studies (Beichler, 2015; Rall et al., 2017). Furthermore, this work provides
322 valuable results also important to the local context of the city of Zagreb by complementing
323 the results of qualitative analysis on focus group data (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a) and other
324 recent research on the UGI in Zagreb (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2017; Kičić et al., 2020).

325 The gathered sample of 94 participants is in line with the number of participants involved
326 with research using a similar data collection approach (Lowery and Morse, 2013; Plieninger
327 et al., 2013). Compared to Zagreb's population census, focus group participants were
328 balanced by gender, with slightly more women participating than men. Most age groups were
329 covered, but with an evident underrepresentation of younger age groups and
330 overrepresentation of older participants compared to census data. Also, there was an
331 overrepresentation of participants with higher education and an underrepresentation of
332 participants with lower education. However, overrepresentation women and highly educated
333 participants was also found in similar studies (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2017; Rall et al., 2017;
334 Kičić et al., 2020)

335

336 *4.1. Perception of CES and tree-based UGI in Zagreb*

337 Our results are consistent with literature findings regarding the fact that parks and forests are
338 the most pronounced types of UGI (Rall et al., 2017). Parks are widely explored as being one
339 of the most important green spaces in cities (Brown et al., 2014b; Bertram and Rehdanz,
340 2015; Zwierzchowska et al., 2018; Dade et al., 2020). Throughout Europe, more than 50
341 different motivations for visiting parks and numerous types of enjoyment when visiting were
342 expressed by people (Vierikko et al., 2020). Therefore, it is no wonder that in Zagreb's city
343 districts, parks are also perceived as providers of all CES and acknowledging their role as one
344 of the most important elements of UGI. Placement of parks in the CA biplot near the
345 intersection of axes indicates their role as a foundation for the provision of all CES.

346 Historically important parks such as Maksimir are fairly present in the city of Zagreb.
347 Established in 1794, Maksimir was the first public park in Southeast Europe (Maruševski and
348 Jurković, 1992). It is certainly the most well-known and popular park even for people who do
349 not live in Zagreb. However, since focus groups were conducted with residents in each city
350 district, researchers learnt about various locally important parks which are important for
351 nearby residents as well as for the entire city, verifying the emerged perception of parks as
352 holders of cultural identity values.

353 Alike parks, forests and park forests are widely explored types of tree-based UGI in relation
354 to human preferences and provision of recreational services (Arnberger, 2006; Ciesielski and
355 Stereńczak, 2018; Korpilo et al., 2018; Baumeister et al., 2020). In this study a large number
356 of markers were collected throughout the city for these tree-based UGI. They were perceived
357 as holders of all explored CES, with an emphasis on recreational use and place attachment
358 values. Due to a significant amount of forested area in Zagreb, this poses an important result
359 for forest planning and management, especially for park forest management where the
360 provision of CES is the main goal.

361 Since this study explored the relationship between the perception of CES and tree-based UGI
362 on a smaller scale, we managed to find types of tree-based UGI less presented in scientific
363 literature that are related to the perception of CES. Some of them are greenways, walking
364 paths along the streams, tree lines, and greenery around residential buildings. Greenways and
365 walking paths along the stream in Zagreb are perceived mostly in relation to place
366 attachment, aesthetics, and recreational values, collecting the above-average number of
367 spatial markers. Greenways are important for citizens since they are large, open, and
368 accessible green areas in the city. The revealed perception and use of greenways in Zagreb is
369 comparable to the perception expressed for Caldes Stream Corridor in Barcelona, where
370 recreational, cultural, and aesthetic values were highlighted for the area (Garcia et al., 2017).
371 With its historical and cultural significance, the greenway is also perceived as part of the
372 cultural identity values in Zagreb; however, it is not perceived as a provider of educational
373 services neither quantitatively nor qualitatively (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). The reason may
374 be the lack of infrastructure and organized activities or not meeting certain expectations that
375 of the participants in terms of educational potential (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). Walking
376 paths along the streams are an important element in cities that contribute to the spatial
377 connectivity of the UGI. Water is an important element in the urban landscape that together

378 with accessibility influences the perception and use of green spaces in cities (Scott Shafer et
379 al., 2013)

380 Perception of tree lines in the context of CES has not been so often mentioned in scientific
381 literature. Trees are an important building element of UGI not just from an ecological point of
382 view, but also psychological and aesthetic (Tyrväinen et al., 2005). Aesthetic benefits arise
383 from colours, textures, forms and densities (ibid.). Tree lines in Zagreb's city districts are
384 predominantly perceived as holders of different aesthetic experiences. With more than 200
385 km of tree lines in Zagreb, this result is important for tree planning and management practices
386 in Zagreb. A recent study from Porto shows that tree lines are mostly valued for
387 environmental services. However, cultural ecosystem services prove to be almost equally
388 important (Graça et al., 2018). Further, research shows that aesthetics is almost universally
389 highly appreciated and an important category of CES in cities (Kytä et al., 2013; Buchel and
390 Frantzeskaki, 2015; Dou et al., 2017; Ives et al., 2017).

391 Cemeteries are perceived as valuable places in cities, holding restorative potential for the city
392 dwellers. This potential emerges from the combination of highly maintained natural elements,
393 especially trees and flowers, quiet environment, recreational potential, along with historical
394 and cultural values they hold (Nordh et al., 2017). Cemeteries in Zagreb resulted in being
395 perceived as holders of aesthetic experiences. Although cemeteries are an important part of
396 UGI and partake in the provision of CES, they were less perceived in Zagreb. This could be
397 due to a data collecting approach where only UGI located within the city district were
398 discussed, while not every district has a cemetery that they could refer to.

399 The greenery around residential buildings is important for everyday use, although it is still an
400 under-explored type of UGI (Säumel et al., 2021). Our participants perceived those spaces
401 more in the context of aesthetics and less in regard to active use. This is similar to the results
402 of the aforementioned study where passive uses are preferred over active ones and where the
403 majority of residents perceived enjoying of natural sounds and different plants and trees
404 (ibid.). There was also a higher appreciation of aesthetics in residential green spaces than of
405 recreation possibilities (Mao et al., 2020). Characteristics of this UGI type could be the
406 reason why they are not more important in terms of (active) recreation in Zagreb, e.g., they
407 are too small for long-lasting or long-distance activities (running or riding a bicycle), or they
408 lack the equipment that people prefer for recreational purposes. This might be in contrast to a
409 recent Swedish study showing that recreationists use nearby landscape types regardless of

410 landscapes characteristics (Lehto et al., 2022). However, this type of UGI was perceived as a
411 provider of all CES, hence indicating a need for further exploration. Private gardens were
412 associated with similar perceptions as greenery around residential buildings, although they
413 were less mentioned by participants. A possible explanation for this is that half of the
414 participants live in apartment buildings and therefore do not have a private garden to refer to.
415 However, private gardens presented an important refuge place during COVID-19 pandemic
416 (Poortinga et al., 2021).

417 Education is usually weakly perceived or explored as a benefit of UGI (O'Brien et al., 2017;
418 Lopez et al., 2021). Educational service (education in nature) was the least perceived CES
419 provided primarily by forests, parks, and greenery of educational facilities. The results of
420 qualitative analysis of focus group interviews show that the educational services also elicited
421 a weak discussion among the participants (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). The reason may be
422 that people have different ideas of what education in nature is or should be. For some
423 participants, any green space can be used for educational purposes, and for others, those UGI
424 should have certain attributes, such as being close to educational institutions as in our case
425 (kindergartens, schools, or faculties), having certain facilities or at least nametags on trees.
426 Teaching outdoors is part of the school curricula in Croatia and school gardens are designed
427 with the aim of education, hence our results and perception participants hold towards them
428 are in line with their primary function. Nevertheless, educational values are difficult to
429 spatially capture, which is a conclusion similar to one proposed for the city of Berlin (Rall et
430 al., 2017).

431

432 *4.2. Patterns in CES perception*

433 The patterns in CES perception regarding tree-based UGI in Zagreb were explored by
434 employing CA and complemented with calculating correlations. Aesthetics emerged as
435 differently perceived from other CES categories in relation to tree-based UGI, forming the
436 first perception bundle. Recreation and place attachment and their respective connected tree-
437 based UGI influenced the second bundle of perception mainly characterized with tree-based
438 UGI having a utilitarian character. Larson et al. (2019) came up with similar results by
439 distinguishing two subdivisions of perception of ecosystem services in a neighbourhood
440 environment – one connected with aesthetic experiences and the other with recreational
441 values and possibilities. The CES categories of place attachment and recreation are highly

442 correlated in relation to their manifestation in tree-based UGI, supporting the claim that
443 recreation can be an underlying goal for interaction with green spaces (Riechers et al., 2016;
444 Krajter Ostoić et al., 2020a). Correlation between the perception of CES categories resulted
445 in high and significant correlation coefficients among some of them. This can indicate similar
446 perceptions and use of those UGI types (Riechers et al., 2019).

447 Although parks are perceived as providers of all CES, other types of tree-based UGI can be
448 associated with specific purposes and perception. This information could be of interest to
449 decision-makers and planning experts, and it is also a valuable starting point for researchers
450 when exploring further tree-based UGI and the perception of CES. Even though patterns of
451 CES provision were detected, high and significant correlation coefficients among variables
452 indicate that most of the CES categories are not stand-alone, but they spatially coexist and
453 synergistically act in the perception of people. Finally, the results show a more synergistic
454 nature of CES (Plieninger et al., 2013; Rall et al., 2017). This adds to the need for the
455 assessment of mutual relationships among ecosystem services (proposed by Haase et al.,
456 2014).

457

458 *4.3. Perception of tree-based UGI in Zagreb in a broader context*

459 Zagreb as a postsocialist city shares some of the problems with other similar cities in Eastern
460 Europe, such as the shift to neoliberal market capitalism which impairs the importance of
461 green spaces at the expense of construction sites (Kronenberg et al., 2020). A serious threat
462 for postsocialist cities is the ownership change from public to private and loss of green space.
463 For example, Bucharest in Romania lost 34.5% of its urban parks to impervious surfaces,
464 consequently influencing the perception and use of green spaces (Iojă et al., 2011). A similar
465 outcome was also observed in Poland (Kronenberg et al., 2021). In Zagreb, with no structured
466 inclusion of citizens in green space management other than a public exhibition of plans to the
467 (un)interested public, public participation is acknowledged as one of the elements of urban
468 green space governance that needs to be improved (Krajter Ostoić, 2013).

469 Exploring the perception and satisfaction with green spaces in Zagreb and other cities that
470 emerged from the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, differences in perception
471 and satisfaction with UGS were found (Krajter Ostoić et al., 2017). Some of them are
472 differences in the perception of general green space importance, the need for more green
473 spaces, or the importance of various negativities such as litter, access to green spaces or

474 vandalism. This indicates that although these cities share similar development practices due
475 to shared history, the local context is also important in exploring the perception of UGI. The
476 results of this research are in line with previous research related to UGI in postsocialist cities,
477 which also enables comparison with the results obtained in western European cities and
478 across different types of tree-based UGI (Garcia et al., 2017; Rall et al., 2017; Säumel et al.,
479 2021).

480

481 *4.4. Limitations*

482 Participatory mapping on a small scale can yield a more detailed view of the city district's
483 UGI, but practitioners should be careful when aiming at the generalization on a city scale for
484 planning purposes due to the purposive sample of participants and the diversity of spatial
485 characteristics in each city district. Furthermore, sociodemographic background of our
486 participants is not representative of the city's population. However, our approach enabled
487 finding patterns that would not otherwise be possible.

488

489 **5. Conclusions**

490 In this paper, we quantitatively explored the interrelation between the perception of CES and
491 tree-based UGI in the city of Zagreb in all city districts. The results show that although place
492 attachment, aesthetics, and recreation are more frequently perceived, our participants overall
493 perceived all explored CES on a city district level, even those known as being hard to capture
494 or less pronounced, such as cultural identity and education. Also, we found that besides parks
495 and forests, there are other types of tree-based UGI perceived and used in relation to CES.
496 With specific attention put on tree-based UGI, we demonstrated that UGI that contains trees
497 is an important part of UGI in cities and partakes as a provider of CES. Additionally, this
498 research demonstrates the data collected and the results gathered with an extensive
499 participatory mapping throughout the city of Zagreb and in direct contact with city
500 inhabitants. The results, especially those regarding less pronounced types of tree-based UGI,
501 could help decision-makers, planners, and managers to better address a variety of tree-based
502 UGI types and maintain them in a way that they keep providing various CES to citizens.

503

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523

524 **Conflict of interest**

525 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

526

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744 **Supplementary Material**

745 *Table 1 - Contribution of CES over the first four dimension of CA (abbreviations as follows: PA – Place Attachment, AES –*
 746 *Aesthetics, REC – Recreation, CI – Cultural Identity, EDU – Education)*

	Dim 1	Dim 2	Dim 3	Dim 4
PA	2.980242	5.4370986	55.869346	2.379980
AES	61.875001	8.6385048	1.353007	0.582466
REC	3.656283	24.9425464	39.507239	9.615019
CI	11.856987	0.4125539	1.716304	75.469937
EDU	19.631487	60.5692962	1.554103	11.952597

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Table 2 - Contribution of tree-based UGI over the first four dimension of CA

	Dim 1	Dim 2	Dim 3	Dim 4
Park	6.5578499	6.3222857	9.0545719	6.9794680
Forest	0.2216858	1.5832821	5.6684760	5.3140090
Park forest	18.5029425	7.7045035	33.7060974	11.7552239
Greenery of Sport and Recreational Facility	1.3261706	5.4093754	22.1099089	5.1874029
Tree line	29.7764627	5.0878173	15.3183670	4.8752959
Walking Path along the Stream	4.3876004	11.6212924	0.6752529	21.8105900
Greenway	0.8696376	11.7601464	1.5465193	4.4201262
Greenery around Residential Buildings	8.5066357	0.7637458	3.4598364	2.8791518
Greenery of Educational Facility	7.8235109	16.8907608	0.3454544	4.5370287
Private Garden	0.3200424	11.0687580	1.8299156	4.0280293
Single Tree	13.1569705	4.1864041	1.7996283	1.2441415
Green System	4.1648339	16.2061604	3.8860959	26.5548190
Cemetery	4.3856568	1.3954680	0.5998761	0.4147138

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